
Implementation of Sustainable Tourism in Eastern Indonesia: A Study on Morotai Island

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ABSTRACT : Sustainable tourism development has become one approach used by many regions in promoting the development of its territory in Indonesia. Its implementation is not going smoothly because it is not easy to find a balance between economic, social, and environmental aspects. So the purpose of this research is to analyze the implementation of sustainable tourism on the island of Morotai. Qualitative methods are used to analyze the focus of research. Primary and secondary data are collected using interviews, library studies, and observations to research informants. Various data already collected from the field are analyzed using data reduction stages, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. The results of the study show that the development of tourism on the island of Morotai is already developing. Mainly leading to the development of sustainable tourism that reflects economic, socio-cultural, and environmental aspects. However, the socio-cultural and environmental aspects have not received attention, so both aspects need to be strengthened in the future. This research contributes to the development of sustainable tourism studies in eastern Indonesia.

KEYWORDS -Sustainable Tourism Development, Morotai Island, East Indonesia

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of tourism in Indonesia has led to a sustainable tourism development approach. The integration of economic, socio-cultural and environmental elements became the main obstacle in the formulation of tourism development in Indonesia. In the development of tourism development in Indonesia still prioritize the economic element by pursuing the amount of income from tourism activities and encouraging the increase of tourist visits. Environmental protection is not the primary concern. This is a challenge in the development of sustainable tourism in Indonesia.

According to the Future Tourism Development Paradigm set out in the medium-term long-term plan (RPJMN) 2020-2024, Quality Tourism Experience is the primary goal for future tourism development. This paradigm consists of several key targets, including increasing the value of the tourism industry, strategic partnerships, market readiness and tourism industries, superior and competitive SDM capabilities, citizens' economic movements, and increased courage. This will impact, i.e. encourage sustained tourism in the tourist area. (Kemenparekraf, 2020; Putri, 2022).

Different regions in Indonesia make the tourism sector the driving force of the economy in their region. The development of new tourist destinations continues to emerge with the hope of boosting investment and opening up jobs. But on the other hand, the threat of environmental damage as a result of massive tourism development cannot be allowed. We need serious attention from the government and tourists. According to Arida (2017) economic activity should not be focused on the use of natural resources and the environment alone, which can ultimately threaten ecological functioning.

The attractiveness of tourism in Indonesia is so diverse, so many neighboring countries want to learn and get to know more about Indonesian tourism. This is due to the diversity of Indonesian races, tribes,

languages and cultures. Tourists can enjoy the natural and cultural beauty of the whole region from Sabang to Merauka (Musaddad, et al, 2019).

One of the tourist destinations that has potential attractions is the island of Morotai. As an outstanding destination established by the Indonesian government, Morotai Island has natural wealth and historical heritage from World War II. Thus, it has a competitive attraction in tourism competition in Indonesia and globally. However, the development of tourism in Morotai did not go smoothly and gained various barriers. So this became the focus of research that discussed the implementation of tourism with a sustainable tourism approach on the island of Morotai.

A lot of the same research has been done before. Susilo and Dharmawan (2021) used environmental sociology approaches in discussing sustainable tourism. The results provide an overview of the use of environmental sociology in sustainable tourism which concludes that there is non-sustainable and sustained tourism. Yatmaja research (2019) shows that, based on public involvement in the development of tourism, the stage of empowerment of the community has not been performed optimally. However, Pokdarwis Minang Rua Bahari has had the ability to build programs and create innovations in tourism management. While Setiono et al, (2021) in his study explains that empowering local communities is the key to sustainable tourism growth. From the results of the above studies, the difference between the previous studies and this study has differences in the analytical indicators, where the researchers use the principles of sustainable tourism as their indicators so different from the previous research above.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

II.1 Implementation of public policy

An essential step in the development of public policy is implementation. Every public policy that has been established since is applied to the intended audience. This is consistent with Edwards III's (1990) assertion that a policy's success is determined by how well it is implemented. Implementation is defined as "the implementation of basic policy decisions, typically in the form of a law, but can also be like important executive orders or decisions or decisions of a judicial body," according to Mazmanian and Sabatier (1983). The decision often outlines the issues that must be solved, the objectives that must be met, and various ways to organize or assess the implementation process. Implementation, according to Agustino (2012), is "a dynamic process, in which the policy maker performs one or more activities, in order to ultimately obtain a hassle that corresponds to the objectives or objectives of the policy itself." From the foregoing defense, it can be inferred that one of the phases in public policy that determines whether the policy goes as intended or not is the implementation of a policy.

II.2 Concept of Construction Continues

According to Baiquni (2002), sustainable development necessitates ecological and economic integration processes that go beyond paradigm formulation initiatives and policy approaches that place an emphasis on collaboration and involvement of development actors in resource management as effectively as possible. Sustainable tourism development is characterized by four factors, according to Yaman&Mohd (2004): 1) Community members need to be involved in the planning and development of tourism; 2) Hosts, industry actors, and visitors and tourists need to be educated; 3) Wildlife habitat quality, energy use, and microclimate need to be understood and supported; 4) Investment in alternative modes of transportation needs to be made.

II.3 Introduction to Continuing

The concept of sustainable tourism was initially introduced by the World Commission on Environment and Development by supplementing sustainable Tourism with the word "development" to "sustainable tourist development". So it means to be "part of the sustainable development that takes into account the needs of the present by considering the needs (living) of future generations in the future time". Sustainable tourism is defined by the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) as tourism that fully considers the current and future economic, social, and environmental implications, while also addressing the requirements of travelers, the

tourism sector, the environment, and host communities. Sustainable tourism is defined by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) as the fusion of tourist demands and travel destinations' prospects to become even more alluring in the future. (WTO, 2004).

Fandeli (2004) defined sustainability as: (1) ensuring environmental quality and sustainable use of natural resources (environment sustainable); (2) greater social sustainability; (3) assuring community cultural sustainability; and (4) not only being economically advantageous to the parties involved but also significantly allocating funds to improve and improve the environmental quality of regions and surrounding communities. (Sustainable economy).

II.4 Principles of Continuity

Mowfort and Munt (1998) outlined the following aspects of sustainable tourism development:

a. Ecological Sustainability

The meaning of ecological sustainability in building sustainable tourism should always pay attention to the ecological system and the living environment that is already the basis of life. Don't make changes that don't follow the laws of nature that apply universally. For example, deforestation, or defecating protected forests, would clearly destroy living resources that are clearly contrary to the resilience of the ecological system itself.

b. Social Adaptability

It is meant in developing tourism that there should be a conformity or agreement between the parties that develop tourism with the local population. (local people). Often it happens, local residents are only spectators in their own villages, because they are not involved in the implementation of tourism projects. Social adaptation in the development of tourism is precisely necessary, especially with ecosystems. Do not the inhabitants of the area know and even know more about how to feed plants, or animals that fit their habitat?

c. Cultural Sustainability

The sustainability of local culture in the efforts to develop sustainable tourism should get attention. Because the cultural art of a nation is the wealth (assets) must be preserved and not to contamination or commercialization of cultural art for the sake of economic gain. Every nation that develops tourism as an industry should always maintain the personality of its people and never follow the behavior of tourists who come to visit.

The Strategic Plan for Sustainable Tourism and Green Jobs for Indonesia, created by the Ministry of Tourism of the Republic of Indonesia in collaboration with the International Labour Organization, explains in Gunawan & Ortis (2012) that tourism plays a sustainable role in addressing social, cultural, and economic issues like poverty reduction and rural development. The strategy's dimensions in terms of the economy, society, and environment are as follows:

a. Reducing Poverty and Rural Development

In order to reduce poverty, respect socio-cultural empowerment, and manage natural resources responsibly, sustainable tourism not only encourages but also enables and empowers communities to participate in the production process and to reap the rewards of such activities.

b. Culture and Society

It is important to consider how tourism affects the social and cultural landscape of the host community. In addition to identifying and managing any negative effects, sustainable tourism techniques aim to promote the beneficial effects of tourism development on regional social and cultural values. By incorporating local culture into or even as the core of tourism products, the sustainable approach to tourism development improves the environment for communities and forges partnerships that are mutually beneficial. Communities can be strengthened by education, communication, fostering tolerance and respect, intercultural interaction, cooperation, and peace.

III. RESEARCH METOHODS

The research design used is a qualitative method. This method is an attempt to explore and understand the meaning of the phenomenon of a social problem. (Creswell, 2012). The source in this study are parties judged competent in their respective fields related to the research topic of implementation of sustainable tourism policy. The type of data used in this study consists of primary and secondary data. Primary data sources are obtained through observations and interviews with informants at the research site. Secondary data is obtained through documentation studies related to documents related to these research topics. In order to answer the research problem, it is necessary to undermine the collection of data. The data collection techniques used in this study consist of observations, interviews, and documentation studies. Interview data, observations and documentation are subsequently processed using analytical techniques consisting of data reduction, data presentation, conclusion drawing.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Construction of tourism on the island of Morotai

The development of the tourism sector in the Moroccan island district is so fast compared to other districts/cities in the Northern Maluku province. Because Morotai Island is made as a Special Economic Area (KEK) by the Central Government so that it encourages the development of various basic infrastructure such as roads and bridges to support the accessibility of tourist activities in the region.

The choice of Morotai as a national tourism development area does not miss out on so many tourist potential that exists in this region. As an area of the former World War II made Morotai have various legacy roles from Japan and the United States. Then the conditions of the territory surrounded by so many small islands make the natural charm of Morotai Island so beautiful and enchanting. The beaches and underwater beauty of the small islands are so rich in the diversity of the sea, so the view is so exotic when compared to elsewhere in Indonesia.

Morotai Island was used as an air base during World War II for Allied armies under General McArthur. That all has become the potential tourist island of Morotai to be developed into an outstanding tourist destination in Indonesia. Because of such attractions as the underwater beauty with the wealth of coral reefs, the charm of the wreckage of warships and fighter jets sunk during World War II, the silence, isolation and peace of its coastline, and the still original beach exotism are a number of advantages that are not found in any other tourist destination in Indonesia.

The development of tourism in the Morotai Island district is divided into several types of tourist attractions, namely, natural tourism attraction, historical tourist attraction and artificial tourism attractions. From the direction of tourism development in the Moroccan island district above, it can be said that Morocco has a rich and diverse tourist potential. The attractiveness of natural tourism becomes the main in driving the increase in the number of tourist visits to Morotai.

The management of various potential tourist attractions in the Moroccan island district that many show its natural charm has not been managed to the maximum. This can be seen from the level of development of tourist attractions and tourist attraction as well as the visits of tourists to several tourist objects in the Morotai Island district that are not maximum.

2. Continuing Tourism on The Island of Morotai

The development of tourism in the Morotai Island district gained the attention of the Central Government through the policy of this special economic area (KEK) tourism. As a result, access to various tourist destinations on the island of Morotai is growing. The development of tourism in Morotai is guided by the KEK Mortai which is directed at the district of South Mortai and the island of Mortai. Morotai's KEK policy has a geostrategic advantage because its position is on the northeastern side of Indonesia which is close to the ASEAN and East Asian countries. In addition to being a historic tour, KEK Morotai also has the advantage of sea tourism with the beauty of the beach and underwater fascinating. Fine white sand, clear sea water and beautiful coral reefs are a tourist attraction in KEK Morotai. Not only that, this area has become a source of

promotion of raw materials for fishing processing industry, because the sea of Morotai is the migratory route of tuna that is recorded by the Indonesian islands III.

The adoption of a tourism development plan that took into account the variety, singularity, and idiosyncrasies of culture and nature, as well as the requirements of people to travel, led to the development of tourism in the Morotai Island area. tourist institutions, the travel and tourist sector, and travel destinations are all covered by tourism development policy. The national rule for the creation of the Moroccan island district, which is connected with the growth of its tourist, supports this as well.

The support of the Central Government to encourage the acceleration of tourism development of Morotai Island has had a significant impact on local communities. Various centres of economic activity have begun to emerge to supplement the needs of tourists when visiting Morotai Island. In addition, services sectors related to tourism activities are also started to be formed by community groups or facilitated by the local government.

In encouraging the participation of local citizens to manage various tourist activities, then the local government forms a tourist conscious group (Pokdarwis) in each tourist destination. Pokdarwis as a group of citizens living in this tourist area has been given a mandate to participate in the management of various tourist activities in its territory. This community's goal is to make citizens feel that they have every tourist object in their village and are able to maintain various tourist facilities that have been built by the government. In addition, Pokdarwis is also an institution of the role of the community to participate in the management of tourist activities. This institution is very important so that the management of tourist destinations can run in accordance with the standards that have been agreed together within the group. Then the presence of Pokdarwis also provides certainty to local citizens to get their role in managing every tourism activity.

Pokdarwis has a number of tasks within managing a tourist object. The main task is to ensure that the various tourist attractions offered to tourists can walk and in safe and comfortable conditions. Because the purpose of people travelling is to get experience and comfort from somewhere. So hospitality in management should be the oversight of every staff involved in Pokdarwis. In addition, Pokdarwis is expected to provide maximum service to each visitor. Especially providing various support facilities needed by the community when traveling.

The presence of Pokdarwis in every tourist object is also able to organize various activities that can provide comfort for tourists. Pokdarwis provides places for food business operators in tourist locations that can be used by local residents to be used as a place to sell. It aims to enable citizens to engage in managing economic activities that are part of the impact of tourism presence in their territory. The existence of a place to eat is one of the facilities that are very needed by tourists, because usually the tourists after finishing enjoying the charm of nature and relaxing in the tourist area then immediately want to eat or consume the various dishes offered by the merchants in a tourist location.

Pokdarwis also initiated the formation of various art groups to be prepared to provide a tourist attraction when there are visitors who want to see or see cultural attractions in the tourist area. The formation of art-cultural groups by Pokdarwis has a mission for the preservation of culture in the local area. In addition to having the goal of making culture as one of the tourist attractions, but Pokdarwis also has the aim of preserving the cultural heritage that exists in its region. However, it should be noted that the long-term use or exploitation of culture for the benefit of tourists also has a negative impact. Because it can reduce the various cultural values that exist in every cultural attraction or can be said as cultural commercialization. The presence of cultural or cultural heritage left behind by the ancestors has no purpose of time that can be used as a time of cultural commercialization. It means that culture is inherited to its children not to be traded through tourist attractions for wise men. Where they pay to watch or watch every show in a tourist location.

The boundary between cultural attractions and local cultural protection in the context of tourism does not have clear boundaries. It is difficult to make a precise boundary so that culture does not fall into the category of cultural commercialization. However, cases in many areas related to cultural commercialization have reached the most concerned point. As is the case in Bali, where tourists pay a lot of money to watch various traditional dances that contain cultural values and Bali customs. For some, commercialization of culture is unjustified.

Because cultural value as a legacy has no purpose to be traded, so it can reduce the content of its continental value.

Various tourism activities in the Morotai island district above have reflected the implementation of sustainable tourism. Where tourist activities that provide participation space for the community around the tourist area to participate in managing its territory as a tourist venue. Then in tourism activities there is the empowerment of local communities in giving roles to manage tourist activities. For example, a small food business in the tourist area. Travel guide service for visitors at the tourist location. In addition, there are efforts to preserve local culture through education to the younger generation to know and practice every cultural heritage that has high values of local socio-cultural life. These are representations of the elements contained in sustainable tourism: economic, socio-cultural, and environmental elements.

3. Updated Principles of Continuous Tourism

In the development of sustainable tourism, several elements form the foundation for its implementation. In the context of tourism development in the island of Morotai can be seen the application of the principles of sustainable tourism as follows:

a. Social culture

The art and culture that exists in the Moroccan Island district mostly have similarities with those in the Northern Halmahera district. This indication is due to the dominant tribes in the Morotai Island district are Tobelo and Galela tribes. As for the art and culture still inherited to this day, among others: Tide-Tide, Cakalele, Denge-denge, Bobaso, Salumbe, Tokuwela, Yangere, Dance KabataTalaga Lina, Tegal. Traditional music types include BambuTiup Music, Gala, BambuHitada Music, Yangere Music, and Marriage Traditions. The cultural diversity of art is still strongly rooted in the Morotai society. This can be a capital in the potential development of tourism to develop.

Historical relics that are still original plus cultural heritage that most of them have not experienced much change will make tourists who want to gain knowledge, see and experience their own life that is different with their patterns and customs, very impressed by what they encounter in Morotai Island District. Moreover, most traditions are still growing and developing as they are.

The historical and cultural aspects of local communities show that there is a network of historic and unique communities and lives, a strong historical charm and there are many things in the life of communities that cannot be found in the society in Indonesia in general. Rituals – the customary rituals they perform show a particular uniqueness, which is impressive for foreign tourists who intend to gain cultural wealth from and in their activities.

There is a strong pride among citizens over their ability to preserve the ancient customs inherited by their ancestors. This will facilitate and streamline efforts to preserve the local culture that will then become one of the tourist attractions of special interest.

b. The Environment

The natural conditions made as a tourist destination are still awake from damage that could potentially disrupt the ecosystem of living creatures in the area. But what needs to be cautious by managers and governments is the garbage produced from various tourism activities. For example, in Dodola Island, which is one of the top tourist destinations of Morotai Island, the problem of garbage is faced. Waste from travel or shipment garbage. Waste from tourists is generated from various activities of tourists around Dodola Island. Whereas the shipment of garbage is the rubbish that is below the sea stream and pollutes the beach area of Dodola Island. It is located in the surrounding area of Dodola Island.

In addition to Dodola Island, garbage is also a problem faced by some tourist destinations on Morotai Island. Therefore, the handling of garbage in the tourist objects should be taken seriously. Efforts to encourage the awareness of tourists to take part in improving hygiene in the location of tourist objects should be a common concern. Tourist facility managers should continuously inform visitors to dispose of garbage at their place. The problem of plastic garbage from tourist activities is a problem in the management of tourist destinations in Indonesia. The active role of the tourist by encouraging the participation of tourists to maintain hygiene in the

location of tourist objects should be a primary concern. The management of garbage cannot be handed over to one party, but it must be the joint responsibility of the carrier, the government, and the tourists. When everyone has the same awareness of environmental hygiene, the sustainability of a tourist destination will happen and become a legacy for future generations.

c. Economy

Tourism efforts in the Moroccan island district have grown quite well, but are still concentrated in urban areas. This is due to the ability of entrepreneurs in the countryside is still very minimal, also limited market access between sellers and buyers due to obstructed transportation connections between one island with another island in Morotai.

It was noted that the number of tourist facilities in the Morotai Island district totaled 43 pieces, with details; restaurants / dining facilities totaled 26 pieces, massage panti / spa 5 pieces, BPW that sold special tickets totaled 2 pieces and hotels totaled 19 pieces (star = 3 pieces and non-star = 15 pieces). From the details it is clear that the combination of tourist facilities is already sufficient, but the problem is that the distance is too far to Morotai Island district because it has to transit in Ternate either by sea or aircraft.

In the Moroccan island district, a number of tourism facilities have been provided by the local government to support the advancement of outstanding tourist destinations. Hospitality or accommodation, restaurant or dining house. From the data obtained by the Tourism Department of the Morotai Island District there are 17 hotels or accommodations that are provided to support excellent tourism facilities, including Molokai hotels, Dloha Resorts, SinggaDulu, Ria, Sintayu, Permai Indah, Antrimel, Marina Putri, Perdana, Pacific Inn, Dodola, Morotei Inn, Agung, Mutiara Inn, Tonga, Moromadoto, and Nakamura accommodation. As for tourism facilities such as restaurants or dining houses, there are 28 restaurants and dining homes spread across the island district of Morotai.

Meanwhile, for the public tourism facilities that support the level of tourist visits to the Moroccan island district has been very complete. In the area of the island of Morotai has been available a variety of facilities such as clean water supply, internet and communication networks, electricity, roads and bridges, ports, airports or airports. In addition there are also office centers, hospitals, pharmacies, banks, shopping centres, restaurants, beauty salons, barbershop, police offices, glasses shops, magazines, gasoline pumps, car workshops, and others.

In addition to the city center, the impact of tourism activities on economic activities also occurs in villages that have tourist objects. Some villages appear to have been built into culinary centers, where local communities are the managers of the enterprise. This makes tourism activities have an economic impact on local communities living close to the tourist area of Morotai Island.

V. CONCLUSION

The development of tourism in the Morotai island district is very developed because this area is made as a tourist cake by the central government. Various facilities that support tourist activities have been slowly shut down, especially access roads to tourist destinations. In its development, tourism activities on the island of Morotai have reflected environmental, economic, and social aspects as the embodiment of the principles of sustainable tourism. So at this stage it can be concluded that the tourism activities on the island of Morotai have implemented the concept of sustainable tourism. But what the government needs to pay attention to in tourism development is not to too pursue the economic aspects to ignore the environmental and social aspects. Because it can disrupt the continuity of tourism development activities on the island of Morotai.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Kemenparekraf. (2020). Renstra-Kemenparekraf- Baparekraf-2020-2024.
- [2] Putri, D. A. P. A. G. (2022). Green Tourism Sebagai Kunci Pariwisata Berkelanjutan. *Pariwisata Nusantara*, 49.
- [3] Arida, I. N. S., & Sunarta, N. (2017). Pariwisata berkelanjutan. *Pariwisata Berkelanjutan*.
- [4] Musaddad, A. A., Rahayu, O. Y., Pratama, E., Supraptiningsih, S., & Wahyuni, E. (2019). Pembangunan Pariwisata Berkelanjutan di Indonesia. *Dinamika Administrasi: Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi dan Manajemen*, 2(1).
- [5] Susilo, R. K. D., & Dharmawan, A. S. (2021). Paradigma pariwisata berkelanjutan di indonesia dalam perspektif sosiologi lingkungan. *Jurnal Indonesia Maju*, 1(1), 49-64.
- [6] Yatmaja, P. T. (2019). Efektivitas Pemberdayaan Masyarakat Oleh Kelompok Sadar Wisata (Pokdarwis) Dalam Mengembangkan Pariwisata Berkelanjutan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Administrasi Publik dan Pembangunan*, 10(1), 27-36.
- [7] Setiono, S. T., Afrizal, T., Supriyono, E., Wendra, R. M., & Nurfitriani, A. (2021). Implementasi Pengelolaan Pariwisata Berkelanjutan Di Kota Semarang. *PERSPEKTIF*, 10(1), 26-35.
- [8] Putri, D. A. P. A. G. (2022). Green Tourism Sebagai Kunci Pariwisata Berkelanjutan. *Pariwisata Nusantara*, 49.
- [9] Edward III, George C (edited). (1990). *Public Policy Implementation*. London-England: Jai Press Inc.
- [10] Mazmanian, Daniel H., dan Paul A. Sabatier. 1983. *Implementation and Public Policy*, New York: Harper Collins.
- [11] Agustino, L. (2012). *Dasar-Dasar Kebijakan Publik*. Bandung: CV Alfabeta.
- [12] Baiquni, M. (2002). *Integrasi Ekonomi dan Ekologi: dari Mimpi Menjadi Aksi*. Yogyakarta: Wacana.
- [13] Yaman, A. R., & Mohd, A. (2004). Community Based Ecotourism: New Proposition for Sustainable Development and Environment Conservation in Malaysia, *Journal of Applied Sciences*. Vol. IV, No. 4, pp. 583-589.
- [14] World Tourism Organization (WTO). (2004). *Indicators of sustainable developmen for tourism destination: A Guide Book*. Madrid.
- [15] Fandeli, C. (2004). *Peran dan Kedudukan Konservasi Hutandalam Pengembangan Ekowisata*. Pidato Pengukuhan Jabatan Guru Besar pada Fakultas Kehutanan Universitas Gadjah Mada, diucapkan di depan Rapat Terbuka Majelis Guru Besar Universitas Gadjah Mada pada tanggal 17 Juli 2004 di Yogyakarta.
- [16] Mowforth, M, & Munt, I. (1998). *Tourism and Sustainability New Tourism in the World*. London: Routledge.
- [17] Gunawan, M. & Ortis, O. (2012). *Rencana Strategis Pariwisata Berkelanjutan dan Green Jobs untuk Indonesia*. Kementerian Pariwisata dan Ekonomi Kreatif Republik Indonesia bekerjasama dengan International Labour Organization.
- [18] Creswell, J.W. (2012). *Research Desigh Pendekatan Kualitatif, Kuantitatif, dan Mixed Edisi Ketiga* (terjemahan). Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.